

SHORT COMMUNICATION

THE ROLES OF AGRICULTURAL COOPERATIVES IN AGRICULTURAL MECHANIZATION IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The roles of agricultural cooperative in agricultural mechanization and its inadequate contributed to the low level of agricultural production in Nigeria compare with the population of the country. This paper critically examined the relevance and contribution of agricultural mechanization to the development of the agricultural sector of the economy. The study also discussed the benefits of credit for agricultural mechanization, the roles of cooperatives in agricultural mechanization were discussed, and some recommendations were suggested. In conclusion, in the context of trade liberalization and globalization, the cooperative approach is one of the best means of self-protection for small farmers mainly due to its self-help concept and member's participation. It is therefore vital for government to strengthen cooperative credit and improves the efficiency of agricultural credit supply.

KEYWORDS: Agricultural Cooperatives, Mechanization, Credit, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

The Nigeria domestic economy is partly determined by agriculture which has experienced a rapid growth during the past eight years. Agriculture has remained the fastest growing sector in the non-oil sector. Agriculture has recorded the growth rate well above 5% in recent years compared with the less than 2% growth of early 80's (Falusi, 2008). In 2005, agriculture contributed 6.8% out of the 8.2% growth rate recorded by the entire non-oil sector (NEEDS, 2008). This same year, the sector also employed about 65 million persons and contributed about 41% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The agricultural GDP is contributed by Crops (85%), Livestock (10%) and Forestry (1%) (NBS, 2007). This growth rate is essential for fostering economic development in the country.

Nigeria with a population of about 144 million and a growing rate of 3.2% per annum, if not checked, the population of Nigeria would double in less than 25 years (Oladipupo, 2008). This alarming growth rate is a challenge in a country where more than 90% of the agricultural output is accounted for by small-scale farmers with less than two (2) hectares under cropping. About 75% (68 million ha) of estimated total Nigeria land has potential for agricultural activities but only about 33 million hectare is under cultivation. Similarly of the estimated 3.14 million hectare irrigable land area only about 220,000 hectares (7%) is utilized (FMAWR, 2008).

In addition, more than 90% of Nigeria agricultural output is accounted for by households with less than 2 hectares under cropping with typical farm sizes range from 0.5 hectares in the south to 4 hectares in the north. Supply of agricultural inputs has also been generally sub-optimal, fertilizer consumption of 7kg is one of the lowest in sub-Saharan Africa, less than 10% of irrigable land is under irrigation, farmers have limited access to credit and the existing extension services are grossly inadequate. There is currently one (1) extension worker for 25,000 in Nigeria compared to best practice of one (1) to 500-1000. Mechanized assistance is also grossly inadequate. There are only about 30,000 tractors for all 14 million farming groups/families in Nigeria (Paul Mari Bdliya, 2009).

Also, it is estimated that over 86% of Nigerian farmers and over 90% of farm operations, including bush clearing, land preparation, Planting, weeding, pest control, harvesting and primary processing are still carried out using hand tools. It is further estimated that in the North about 85% of total area cultivated per year employed hand tools, about 6% employed animal power, while about 8% are cultivated with the use of motorized tractors (Aja v, 2000) and about 30-40% of agricultural produce is lost owing to poor post-harvest

handling, storage and processing methods (FAO, 2011). Therefore, the forgoing underscores the importance of agricultural mechanization as a policy instrument in the growth and development of Nigeria's agriculture and need to explore the constraints to agro-mechanization. This paper further attempt to review these issues and the roles cooperatives and credit could play in agricultural mechanization of Nigeria.

Agriculture Mechanization

The traditional technology employed in agriculture holds the investments of land, labour, and capital below a profitable margin which can promote full utilization of resource in Nigeria. This therefore calls for mechanized agriculture. In order to make agriculture profitable and productive, priorities and strategies should be shifted to the use of modern mechanization technologies suitable for both the small and medium scale farmers.

Agricultural mechanization therefore means the application of agricultural engineering principles and technology, by the use of mechanical systems in the process of food, feed, fibre, fuel production, protection, processing, handling and storage (Aseogwu, 1998). It also refers to the replacement of manual labour and simple hand tools with human, animal, electrical and internal consisting engine powered machinery (Wikipedia, 2011). Rijk (2011) and FAO (2011) summarized the purpose and aims of agricultural mechanization as follows:

- Increase the power inputs to farming activities, hence putting more land into production
- Reduce drudgery in farming activities, thereby enhancing lifestyles
- Improve the timeliness and efficiency of farm operations
- Accomplish tasks that are difficult to perform without mechanical aids
- Improve the quality and value of work, produce and processed products.
- Provide employment (entrepreneurship) and sustainable rural live hoods
- Provide agricultural-led industrialization and markets for rural economic growth.

Credit for Agricultural Mechanization

Agricultural production generally is capital intensive and in developing countries like Nigeria, small scale farmers need to inject capital into agriculture to increase production. The critical role of credit in economic development has never been in doubt either directly or indirectly in building the capacity of the small-holder farmers in increased agricultural mechanization for household food security and poverty alleviation. With adequate supply of credit to farmers, the retarded agricultural sector will make progress because agricultural credit can stimulate the growth of agriculture, enhanced productivity and promotes standard of living by breaking vicious cycle of poverty of small scale farmers. It also enable farmers to meet their needs, expand their farms increase output, and aids small scale farmers to engage in commercial agriculture (Mohammed, 2009, Adebayo and Adeola 2008).

Regrettably, the availability of credit to the agricultural sector has over the years remained inadequate, and even more so for the agricultural mechanization sub-sector. The analysis in Table 1 below gave an insight of the cumulative trend of loans granted to agriculture under Agriculture Credit and Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) 1996-2005.

Table 1: Trend of Loans Granted to Agriculture under Agriculture Credit and Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) 1996-2005

Year	No of Beneficiaries	Total Amount Grant's ₦000	Average Amount/Beneficiaries ₦000
1996	19,439	25,466.3	1.310
1997	17,839	27,577.5	1.5459
1998	6,428	17,480.6	2.7194
1999	12,657	19,444.0	1.5362
2000	244,495	29,566.0	0.1209
2001	20,298	46,861.8	2.3087
2002	23,681	31,428.7	1.3272
2003	24,304	13,951.0	0.5740
2004	35,035	2,065,254.7	58.9483
2005	37,733	3,046,738.1	80.7447

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin 2006

It can be concluded from the above that formal financial lenders do not favour investment in agricultural mechanization probably due to economic and risk considerations as well as due to limited funds.

Role of cooperatives in agricultural mechanization

Cooperative organizations play very important role in the socio-economic life of the Nation. Cooperative can be identified as an autonomous, association of persons united voluntarily to meet their common, economic, social and cultural needs and aspirations through jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprise. In Nigeria, majority of the agricultural cooperatives at different levels are multipurpose in their function. Not only do they operate banking business, but they also deal with other support series such as input supply, marketing and purchasing which is critical to agricultural mechanization.

The agricultural cooperative handles all kinds of credit including short, medium and long-term credit. It has mobilized a large amount of funds both from rural and urban areas and supplied an increasing amount of credit to farmers. Cooperative organizations have help to reduce some of the problems frequently faced by small scale farmers in obtaining loan such as: high interest rate, collaterals, lack of repayment moratorium and undue bureaucratic bottlenecks. Therefore, the roles expected of cooperatives organizations for the effective realization of agricultural mechanization aims and objectives are as follows:

- Cooperative organizations are expected to provide the appropriate avenue for the demonstration of the modern technologies to meet farmer's needs in agricultural production and processing.
- Cooperative organizations are also to serve as effective intermediaries in the delivery of credit to beneficiary farmers.
- Cooperative organizations are expected to serve as avenue for a more accurate identification of input needs of the farmers.
- Training and adoption of agricultural technologies is made easier through cooperative organizations.
- Dissemination of ideas and information on availability of credit facilities is faster and enhanced.
- Accessing credit facilities is easier and faster through cooperative organizations.
- Cooperative organizations also enhance farmer's standard of living, reduce poverty alleviation and increase farm productivity.

CONCLUSION

Nigeria's agricultural cooperative with multipurpose function, has played a substantial role in breaking vicious cycle of poverty by supply of agricultural cooperative credit. In the context of trade liberalization and globalization, the cooperative approach is one of the best means of self – protection for small farmers mainly due to its self-help concept and member's participation. It is therefore vital for government to strengthen cooperative credit and improves the efficiency of agricultural credit supply.

To further exploit the benefit of credit facilities through cooperatives organization to boost agricultural mechanization in the country the following are suggested:

- Farmers in the country should be advised and encouraged to join cooperative;
- Credit facilities through agricultural cooperative should attract lower interest rate of at least 2-3%
- Financial institutions should endeavor to provide friendly customer service such as reducing bureaucratic bottlenecks and transaction costs.

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